

Possibility of Removing Phosphates from Activated Charbon Made from Date Kernels

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Abstract: Phosphates in natural waters and whatever their origin, promote the formation of algae, reduce dissolved oxygen and reduce biodiversity in aquatic ecosystems. At high doses, phosphate salts can cause health problems. The objective of our study was to develop a simple, efficient and environmentally friendly sorption depollution technique on available and inexpensive media. We have studied the adsorption of phosphate on activated carbons prepared from date kernels. Batch tests were carried out in order to study different operating parameters such as the effect of contact time, pH, initial phosphate concentration and adsorbent dosage and adsorption kinetic. The sorption equilibrium was analyzed by Langmuir, Freundlich isotherms model. Results show that the phosphate adsorption was reversible and the quantity adsorbed reached its maximum value (14.49 mg/g) after 40 minutes. It was also found that phosphate uptake was affected by variation of pH, initial concentration of phosphate and activated carbon dosage. The adsorption improved with an acidic pH (pH = 6), initial concentration and adsorbent dosage. The results of kinetic studies revealed that adsorption phosphate on activated carbon based on date kernels (Biocar) and the intra-particle diffusion involved in the adsorption mechanism. Also, isotherm study showed that Langmuir isotherm best fit the data and the adsorption was a physical type.

1. INTRODUCTION

Phosphates are part of anions that can be assimilated by the body of a human being [1]. Whatever their origin (domestic, industrial or agricultural), their presence in waters with high concentrations (concentrations greater than 0.2 mg / l) promotes the massive development of algae, which lead to the eutrophication of lakes and rivers. of water [2]. There are several conventional processes for the removal of phosphates from contaminated waters such as biological treatments [3,4] and physicochemical processes which are based on precipitation phenomena of calcium salts, iron or aluminum [5] or on coagulation flocculation of aluminum sulphate[6] or by adsorption on clay; [7, 8].

Nowadays, the increasing demand for adsorbent materials for environmental protection processes calls for further research into the production of activated carbon from non-conventional materials, specifically from vegetable waste [9]. Activated carbon is one of the most used adsorbent materials for the filtration of water and liquids. It is a material with an extremely complex porous structure and a very large surface area that can absorb a wide variety of substances. Among the various plant source materials for the production of activated charcoal are: coconut husks, hazelnut and nut almond hulls, apple pulp as well as olive kernels and date kernels [10].

A significant amount of date kernels are generated each year and constitute a significant source of agricultural waste. Such byproducts corresponding to this loss are nevertheless likely to be of significant economic interest. It turns out, therefore,

important to value such waste. The dates kernels have been the subject of various studies for various applications such as adsorption. The aim of our work is to develop a simple, efficient and environmentally friendly sorption depollution technique on available and inexpensive media. We have studied the adsorption of phosphates on raw and active coals prepared by date kernels.

The influence of some relevant factors, including contact time, pH value, initial phosphate content, concentration and adsorbent dosage, are investigated. In addition, the kinetics and sorption of equilibrium studies were performed.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The preparation of the activated carbon from the date nuclei was carried out by chemical activation using phosphoric acid H_3PO_4 as an activating agent. Nut processing involved the following operations:

2.1. The preparation of activated carbons necessarily passes through preliminary stages (collection, carbonization, grinding, sieving, ...).

a) Collecting the dates kernels (variety Deglet- Nour).

In order to valorize local materials inactivated charcoal, we used as precursor dates kernels coming from a region of the southwest Algerian (Biskra) which is an oasis known by its dates of very good quality. The wilaya of Biskra, capital of the Ziban located about 470km south-east of Algiers limited to the north by the wilaya of Batna, to the east by wilaya of Khenchela, the west by wilaya of Msila and Djelfa, south by

wilaya of El-Oued and Ouargla. It is part of the arid region of the country whose climate is of the Saharan type (hot summer and mild winter). The collection was carried out during the months of November and December 2018.

b) Pretreatment of date kernels.

- After separating the date cores from the pulp, we washed the nuclei thoroughly with distilled water to remove the dust and then dried in an oven at 130 °C for 24 hours.
- After 24 hours of drying, the date cores were crushed using a grinder (IKA Werk MF10) Basic and sieved to obtain a fraction with a particle size of between 0.5 and 1 mm. The ground material is retained and stored in airtight containers sealed.

c) Chemical activation.

Chemical activation is activation in the liquid phase: the previously treated material was impregnated in the activating agent and then pyrolyzed under an inert atmosphere. The agent used is: H_3PO_4 . The carbonization and the actual activation are combined in a single step, it requires only a single heat treatment of temperatures between 400 and 800 °C, values below the usual physical activation temperatures. The activating agent, the impregnation rate, the temperature and the duration of the activation are the main parameters of the chemical activation, they condition the properties of the carbons obtained in terms of pore volume, pore size distribution and chemical composition of the surface.

The choice of the activating agent is very often dictated by the nature of the precursor materials (for a given precursor, certain activating agents are better adapted) and by the properties required by the final product [10,11]

In our work, we have opted for phosphoric acid as an activating agent and is widely used for the activation of coals. The stages of preparation and activation of activated charcoal by date kernels are presented in (Fig.1):

4. CONCLUSION

The aim of this work was to assess the phosphate removal by adsorption using activated carbon prepared from date kernels.

- Removal of phosphate ions is a reversible phenomenon and reaches its maximum value after 40 minutes.
- Powdered activated carbon gives better yields and reaches 71.20%. This can be attributed to an important surface area, a macroporosity and surface functions allowing the retention of phosphates.
- The adsorption of phosphate on these adsorbents obeys the Freundlich and Langmuir laws with a maximum capacity of 14.49 mg / g for activated carbon prepared by date kernels. This value shows that the active carbon has a good adsorption capacity because it contains a higher percentage of porous fraction.

- The results obtained show that the activated carbon used has led to better adsorption results of phosphates at an acidic pH (pH = 6). Results show that the granular activated carbon has an important capacity of phosphate ion removal from waters which gives a promising prospect of practical use.

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